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RADNEXT Transnational Access Summary Report

Project title	<i>A 2.56GHz Radiation Hardened All Digital Phase Locked Loop</i>
Project TA identifier	<i>TA09-286</i>
General application	<i>High-energy accelerators</i>
Type of test	<i>SEE</i>
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Date(s) of the experiment	<i>24th April 2024</i>
Facility	<i>University of Jyväskylä/Department of Physics</i>
Amount of access granted (unit of access: 1h)	<i>8h</i>

Objectives of the experiments

The goal of this experiment is to test and optimize the proposed radiation-hardened All-Digital Phase-Locked Loop (ADPLL) with a fast recovery technique. Our previous study observed Single Event Effects (SEEs) in the inductor, which is widely used in LC tank-based oscillators in ADPLL. As a result, the ADPLL suffers from an undesired frequency transient that can last several milliseconds, depending on the loop gain. To accelerate the locking process, we propose a locking state detection block incorporated with a bandwidth switching technique. The proposed ADPLL will first detect if the loop is in a locking state. Once SEEs occur, the bandwidth switching technique will engage to improve the locking speed until the loop is in a locking state again.

[1] S. Biereigel, et al, "Single-Event Effect Responses of Integrated Planar Inductors in 65-nm CMOS," in IEEE TNS vol. 68, no. 11, Nov. 2021

Experiment test report

1. Test setup
 - (1) The test chip is fabricated using TSMC 65 nm and assembled on a DUT daughter PCB board. Only the chip area, including the spiral inductor, is exposed to the heavy ion beam.
 - (2) A mother PCB board, powered at 3.3 V by an external power supply, supplies and communicate with the test chip through PCIe connector.
 - (3) An ultra-low noise clock generation board (Si570) generates reference clock to the ADPLL through SMA cable.
 - (4) A small USB-SPI board programmed by the portable laptop communicates with the test chip through the PCB board.
 - (5) An SDR placed close to the laptop as it has a high communication bandwidth through USB3.0

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measures the ADPLL phase. We connect the output clock through (long) coaxial cables from the bunker to the instrumentation room.

Except for the DUT board, all other instruments can be placed outside the radiation field.

(6) The chip is exposed under three different ions: Xe, Kr, and Ar.

2. Test results

(1) Open loop test

Firstly, open loop tests with three different ion energies were conducted. In the open loop configuration, the output of the ADPLL is directly the oscillator clock output, allowing us to observe the frequency disturbances without the influence of loop dynamics. The maximum peak frequency errors with Xe, Kr, and Ar are 32 ppm, 25 ppm, and 16 ppm respectively. The transition time is almost the same for all three ions, around 35 ms.

(2) Closed loop test without fast recovery technique

Secondly, closed loop tests without the fast recovery technique were conducted using the same ions. The recovery times with Xe, Kr, and Ar are 123 μ s, 115 μ s, and 92 μ s respectively.

(3) Closed loop test with fast recovery technique

Finally, closed loop tests with the fast recovery technique were conducted. The recovery times were reduced to 15 μ s, 13 μ s, and 12 μ s respectively.

3. Conclusion

Our test results shows that our fast recovery technique can largely reduce the frequency transition time due to the SEEs in the inductor.

Outcome of the experiments

Please indicate what the experiment is likely to lead to by putting an 'X' next to one or more of the possible outcomes below.

Journal publication	X
Data for Thesis	X
Follow-up experiment at same facility	
Follow-up experiment at another facility	
Other	

As a RADNEXT user, we encourage you to submit the scientific results of your experiments to journals as well as to the NSREC and RADECS data workshops. Please remember to include the RADNEXT acknowledgment into your publications!

RADNEXT acknowledgment:

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